

Dysregulation of Nitric Oxide/cGMP Pathway: A Pathological Cascade in Vascular Dysfunction

Minahil Shoaib¹, Hafiz Muhammad Haseeb Khaliq¹, Deeba Baig^{1*}

¹Forman Christian College (A Chartered University) Lahore Pakistan

*Correspondence: deebabaig@fccollege.edu.pk

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ABSTRACT

Nitric oxide (NO) and cyclic guanosine monophosphate (cGMP) signaling are integral to regulating diverse physiological processes, particularly within cardiovascular and neuronal systems. The NO/cGMP pathway governs vascular relaxation and blood pressure regulation with help of interactions between endothelial and smooth muscle cells. Dysregulation of this pathway contributes to endothelial dysfunction and is implicated in conditions such as pulmonary hypertension, atherosclerosis, and cardiac hypertrophy. Additionally, aberrations in NO/cGMP signaling are implicated in neurodegenerative diseases like Alzheimer's disease, where NO-mediated neuronal cell death and cognitive impairment occur. This review delves into the complex mechanisms underlying NO/cGMP signaling in both physiological and pathological contexts. In endothelial cells, NO generated via endothelial nitric oxide synthase (eNOS) triggers soluble guanylyl cyclase (sGC) activation in vascular smooth muscle cells, culminating in cGMP-mediated vasodilation. Conversely, disruptions in NO production and cGMP levels contribute to endothelial dysfunction and vascular pathologies. In neuronal cells, NO/cGMP signaling modulates synaptic plasticity and memory formation, yet deviations from this pathway lead to neurodegenerative conditions such as Alzheimer's disease. Comprehending the multifaceted roles of NO/cGMP signaling in health and disease is imperative for developing targeted pharmacotherapies. Novel drug targets encompass NO-donating hybrid medications, CNS-targeting sGC stimulators/activators, and selective PDE inhibitors, all aimed at modulating NO/cGMP pathways to preserve cardiovascular and neuronal health.

Keywords: NO/cGMP pathway, Vascular Dysfunction, Pathology, Cell signaling, pulmonary hypertension, Alzheimer's disease

INTRODUCTION

Nitric oxide/cGMP signaling involves the endogenous pathway in which nitric oxide is produced from L-arginine by nitric oxide synthase present in endothelial cells of pulmonary system. This nitric oxide then diffuses to nearby vascular smooth muscle cells and carries out a signaling cascade to activate intracellular guanylyl cyclase which will do relaxation of smooth muscle cells present in blood vessels and controls the blood pressure. Guanylyl cyclase receptor present in smooth muscle cell surface has ferrous containing heme group in its active site due to which it exhibits high affinity to bind with nitric oxide.

Apart from that, NO/cyclic-GMP signaling is also involved in leukocyte adhesion, synaptic plasticity, inhibiting aggregation of blood platelets.

RELAXATION OF PULMONARY VSMCs (VASODILATION)

This signaling pathway starts when ligand i.e., acetylcholine, bradykinin, histamine binds to N-terminal of ligand specific G-protein coupled receptors which are seven trans-membrane proteins present in pulmonary endothelial cells. Ligand binding to receptor induces a change in conformation of GPCR which allows the inactive heterotrimeric G-protein (bounded to GDP) to bind with the C-terminal of ligand specific GPCR (Joyce C *et al.*, 2019). Another protein guanine nucleotide exchange factor removes the GDP and attach GTP to activate the G-protein. This activated G-protein (bounded to GTP) then dissociates into α and $\beta\gamma$ subunits. The $G_{\alpha q}$ subunit of G-protein activates another protein i.e., Phospholipase C β to cleave the membrane lipid phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP₂) into secondary signaling molecules i.e., inositol 1,4,5-triphosphate (IP₃) and 1,2-diacylglycerol (DAG). DAG activates another enzyme i.e., protein kinase C to phosphorylate the MAP kinases and other substrates to trigger cellular proliferation (Berridge *et al.*, 2014).

IP₃ diffuses from cytoplasmic membrane into the endoplasmic reticulum membrane to bind with IP₃-gated calcium channels and triggers the Ca²⁺ mobilization, thus releasing the calcium ions from lumen of endoplasmic reticulum. The released calcium ions bind to a calcium sensor i.e., calmodulin. This Ca²⁺/calmodulin complex then activates the Ca²⁺/calmodulin-dependent kinase (CaM kinase). This enzyme phosphorylates the endothelial nitric oxide synthase and activates it. Activated eNOS produce nitric oxide from L-arginine and oxygen as follows.

The nitric oxide produced in endothelial cells diffuses into nearby pulmonary vascular smooth muscle cells and binds to NO receptors (sGC receptor) present in SMC. This leads to activation of an enzyme i.e., guanylyl cyclase that will hydrolyze GTP to cGMP and phosphate molecules (PPI). Cyclic-GMP activates protein kinase G (PKG) that will phosphorylate downstream signaling proteins to cause relaxation of smooth muscle cells present in blood vessels (joyce C *et al.*, 2019). PKG phosphorylates and activates the Rho protein. Activated RhoA protein further stimulates the Rho-associated protein kinase (ROCK) which catalyzes the phosphorylation and inactivation of myosin light chain phosphatase (MLCP). When MLCP is activated i.e., non-phosphorylated, it catalyzes the dephosphorylation of MLC and promotes relaxation of smooth muscle cells. On the other hand, cGMP also inhibits GMP phosphodiesterase to prevent conversion of cGMP to GMP. Due to increased cGMP, there will be vasodilation of muscle arteries leading to increased blood flow and lowers the blood pressure (as shown in Figure 1).

PATHOLOGICAL NITRIC OXIDE (NO)/cGMP SIGNALING PATHWAYS

Alterations in production of nitric oxide cause endothelial dysfunction which leads to diseases in cardiac cells, muscle cells

and nerve endings. cGMP levels are disrupted in pulmonary hypertension, atherosclerosis, diabetes etc. Imbalance in vasodilators and vasoconstrictors cause endothelium dysfunction, thus resulting in cardiovascular diseases like cardiac hypertrophy, hypertension and congestive heart failure. Overexpression of nitric oxide plays an important role in neurodegenerative diseases, septic shock and ischemia-reperfusion.

Figure 1: Relaxation of VSMCs via NO/cGMP Pathway

ALZHEIMER DISEASE

The signaling pathway starts when β -amyloid ($A\beta$) protein produced from amyloid precursor protein (APP) binds to GPCR present in neuronal cell membrane of brain (Urszula *et al.*, 2010). This induces a conformational change in GPCR which allows the inactive heterotrimeric G-protein (bound to GDP) to bind with the C-terminal of ligand specific GPCR. GDP is replaced by GTP with help of GEF which activates the G-protein. This activated G-protein (bound to GTP) then dissociates into α and $\beta\gamma$ subunits. The $G_{\alpha q}$ subunit of G-protein activates another protein i.e., Phospholipase $C\beta$. This enzyme converts the phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP_2) to secondary messengers i.e., IP_3 and DAG. Diacylglycerol activates the protein kinase to phosphorylate the MAP kinases and other substrates to trigger cellular proliferation.

IP_3 diffuses from cytoplasmic membrane to the endoplasmic reticulum where it binds to IP_3 -gated calcium receptors (IP_3R) and triggers the Ca^{2+} mobilization, thus releasing the high amount of calcium ions from lumen of endoplasmic reticulum. These calcium ions undergo several pathways to result in neuronal cell death.

The Ca^{2+} /calmodulin complex also activates the Ca^{2+} /calmodulin-dependent kinase (CaM kinase). This enzyme phosphorylates the neuronal nitric oxide synthase and activates it. Activated nNOS produce nitric oxide from L-arginine and oxygen as follows.

The nitric oxide reacts with oxygen to form reactive endogenous nitrogen specie i.e., peroxynitrite ($ONOO^-$). This nitrogen radical produce various abnormal physiological responses such as mitochondrial damage, inflammation, apoptosis which eventually leads to death of nerve cells. The calcium ions also trigger protein phosphatase 2B (PP2B) protein which leads to glycogen synthase kinase 3 (GSK-3) activation, thus phosphorylating tau protein. Phosphorylated tau protein aggregates to form neurofibril tangles in brain thus causing Alzheimer disease. Tubulin A and Tubulin B protein present in microtubules are also deactivated thus resulting in axonal transport defects.

CARDIAC HYPERTROPHY

The endothelial dysfunction of cardiac cells leading to heart failure is mainly due to oxidative stress involving the formation of oxidative radicals which inactivates the nitric oxide (Berridge *et al.*, 2005). Decreased nitric oxide expression leads to hypertrophy of myocytes. The NO/cGMP pathway act as negative regulator to induce cardiac hypertrophy by inhibiting the Ca^{2+} signaling. cGMP may also reduce the activation of myocyte enhancer factor-2 which regulates the foetal gene transcription (Zuchi *et al.*, 2020). Protein mutation also occurs in sarcoplasmic reticulum which leads to enhanced release of calcium ions in cytoplasm. This leads to diastolic dysfunction of left ventricle resulting in left ventricular hypertrophy. Excessive pressure load on arteries leads to activation of reactive oxygen species which reduces the availability of nitric

oxide synthase cofactor i.e., BH₄ leading to decreased nitric oxide and cGMP production, thus resulting in left ventricular hypertrophy and cardiac failure (Tsai *et al.*, 2009).

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Figure 2: Neuronal Cell Death via NO/cGMP Pathway

The NO/cGMP pathway for cardiac hypertrophy involves the binding of ligands such as endothelin-1, angiotensin-2 to G-protein coupled receptors present in cardiac cell membrane of heart. This leads to conformational change in GPCR which allows the inactive heterotrimeric G-protein (bounded to GDP) to bind with the C-terminal of ligand specific GPCR. Another factor GEF replaces the GDP with GTP and activates the G-protein. This activated G-protein (bounded to GTP) then dissociates into α and $\beta\gamma$ subunits. The $G_{\alpha q}$ subunit of G-protein activates another protein i.e., Phospholipase C β . This enzyme converts phosphatidylinositol 4,5-bisphosphate (PIP₂) to secondary transducing molecules i.e., (IP₃) and (DAG).

DAG activates the protein kinase C-alpha (PKCA) which phosphorylates histone deacetylases i.e., HDAC 4,5,7,9 present inside nucleus. After that myocyte enhancer factor-2 (MEF-2) is inhibited by these phosphorylated HDAC. Transcription of foetal genes are not properly regulated, and this results in enhanced protein synthesis and thus cardiac hypertrophy. DAG also activates protein kinase C- β , γ , ϵ which further activates the Ras protein. This leads to activation of Raf 1 kinases. This further activates MAP kinases i.e., MEK1/2 and ERK1/2. These MAP kinases enter the nucleus to activate transcription factors, resulting in hypertrophic protein synthesis leading to cardiac failure.

IP₃ diffuses from cytoplasmic membrane to bind with IP₃R present on endoplasmic reticulum and triggers the Ca²⁺ mobilization, thus releasing the high amount of calcium ions from lumen of endoplasmic reticulum. These calcium ions undergo several pathways to result in cardiac hypertrophy and heart failure. Ca²⁺ ions bind to a calcium sensor i.e., calmodulin. This Ca²⁺/calmodulin complex then activates the CaM kinase (CAMK2D) enters the nucleus to phosphorylate histone deacetylases i.e., HDAC 4,5,7,9. This leads to inhibition of the myocyte enhancer factor-2 (MEF-2). Transcription of foetal genes are not properly regulated, and this results in enhanced protein synthesis and thus cardiac hypertrophy. Ca²⁺ ions also activate calcium/calmodulin dependent phosphatase i.e., calcineurin. Activated calcineurin then dephosphorylates the nuclear factor of activated cells (NFAT) which enters the nucleus to do transcription of genes. Reactive oxygen species reacts with nitric oxide to form reactive endogenous nitrogen specie i.e., peroxy-nitrite (ONOO⁻) in the endothelial cells. This peroxy-nitrite diffuses into cardiomyocytes and inhibits the soluble guanylyl cyclase which leads to decreased cGMP production and inactivation of protein kinase G, thus leading to cardiac hypertrophy.

Atrial natriuretic peptide (ANP) binds to guanylyl cyclase receptor on cardiac cells. This results in conversion of GTP to cGMP by guanyl cyclase. cGMP activates the protein kinase G-1 (PKG1) which inhibits the NFAT thus resulting in unregulated gene transcription leading to hypertrophy and cardiac failure. Phosphodiesterase 5 (PDE5A) is located inside cardiomyocytes and its upregulation will hydrolyze cGMP to GMP, inducing hypertrophy of cardiac cells (Zhang *et al.*, 2008).

Figure 3: Cardiac Failure via NO/cGMP Pathway

PULMONARY ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION

The rise in blood pressure is mainly due to endothelial dysfunction resulting in vasoconstriction of arterial blood vessels. The main reason for hypertension is decrease in production of nitric oxide due to increase superoxide radicals i.e., O_2^- which converts NO to ONOO⁻ (peroxynitrate). These superoxide radicals are produced by enzymes such as nitro-oxygenase (NOX), lipoxygenase (LOX), peroxidase. L-arginine is converted into L-ornithine by arginase II and it prevents the formation of nitric oxide from L-arginine by eNOS and also upregulates the mitochondrial calcium uptake, which leads to vasoconstriction of blood vessels resulting in hypertension (Zhang *et al.*, 2004). The increased expression of phosphodiesterase 1 and 5 reduces the amount of cGMP by converting it into GMP, thus inhibiting vasodilation and relaxation of blood vessels.

The signaling pathway starts when ligand i.e., adrenaline or angiotensinogen binds to N-terminal of specific G-protein coupled receptors (7 transmembrane protein) i.e., adrenergic receptor alpha 1A and angiotensin receptor II type 1 respectively. These receptors are present in vascular smooth muscle cells of pulmonary arteries. Binding of ligand to receptor induces a conformational change in GPCR which allows the inactive heterotrimeric G-protein (bounded to GDP) to bind with the C-terminal of ligand specific GPCR. G-protein is activated when GEF replace the GDP with GTP. This activated G-protein (bounded to GTP) then dissociates into α and $\beta\gamma$ subunits. The $G_{\alpha q}$ subunit of G-protein activates another protein i.e., Phospholipase C β . This enzyme cleaves the membrane lipid (PIP₂) to secondary messengers, inositol 1,4,5-triphosphate (IP₃) and 1,2-diacylglycerol (DAG).

DAG activates the protein kinase C to phosphorylate CPI-17 which is protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 14A. CPI-17 leads to inhibition of myosin light chain phosphatase (MLCP). Inhibited MLCP will not dephosphorylate myosin light chain and it will lead to vasoconstriction of blood vessels due to crossbridge formation between actin and myosin. Protein kinase C also activates Raf kinases which further phosphorylates and activates mitogen activated protein kinases i.e., MEK1/2 and ERK1/2. These MAP kinases phosphorylate and activates the caldesmon to inhibit the ATPase activity of myosin, linking it with actin which results in contraction of arteries leading to hypertension. IP₃ diffuses from cytoplasmic membrane to the endoplasmic reticulum where it binds to IP₃-gated calcium channels and triggers the Ca²⁺ mobilization, thus releasing the calcium ions from lumen of endoplasmic reticulum. The released calcium ions bind to a calcium sensor i.e., calmodulin. This Ca²⁺/calmodulin complex then activates the myosin light chain kinase (MLCK), which will phosphorylate and activate the myosin light chain to form cross-linking with actin filaments and resulting in vasoconstriction of pulmonary arteries.

Atrial natriuretic peptide (ANP) binds to guanylyl cyclase receptor on vascular smooth muscle cells. This results in conversion of GTP to cGMP by guanyl cyclase. Nitric oxide synthesized in pulmonary endothelial cells by eNOS also diffuses into smooth muscle cells to activate the guanylyl cyclase. The cGMP activates the protein kinase G-1. PKG-1 inhibits the Rho protein and activates the ROCK which will activate the myosin light chain kinase to phosphorylate MLC, resulting in vasoconstriction. Protein kinase G phosphorylates the PLC resulting in decreased production of IP₃ secondary messengers to reduce the

calcium release. PKG-1 also inhibits the L-type calcium channels to decrease the influx of extracellular calcium ions. ATP dependent K⁺ channels are activated to cause hyperpolarization of smooth muscle cells thus inhibiting calcium influx by LTCC. Protein kinase G-1 also inhibits phospholamban (PLB) which leads to activation of SERCA pump resulting in increased uptake of calcium ions by sarcoplasmic reticulum, following blood vessel constriction (Thoonen *et al.*, 2013).

Figure 4: Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension via NO/cGMP Pathway

DISCUSSION

Nitric oxide (NO) regulates the phosphorylation process of the transcription factor known as cAMP response element-binding (CREB), which is essential for promoting cell survival and plays a crucial role in synaptic plasticity as well as memory formation (Tropea *et al.*, 2022). It is also seen that nitric oxide signaling in synaptic cleft involves the production of nitric oxide by binding of nNOS to postsynaptic density proteins i.e., PSD-93 and PSD-95. On the other hand, inducible nitric oxide synthase present in macrophages do not require increase in calcium ions for its activation. This recruited pathway increases the NO production to upregulate the inflammatory mediators such as interferon- γ (IFN- γ) to induce inflammation as a defense mechanism against invading microorganisms (Berridge *et al.*, 2014). Decreased production of NO/cGMP in neuronal cells affects the learning and memory behavior. Selective PDE4 inhibitors are used to improve long term memory by enhancing cGMP production. Protein kinase G phosphorylates the pro-apoptotic Bad protein in order to prevent cell death by apoptosis. Superoxide anions reacts with high concentration of nitric oxide to form peroxynitrite and induce apoptosis. Nitrosylation of protein and mitochondrial damage ultimately leads to neuronal cell death. Inhibitors of PDE5 are widely used to prevent apoptosis and treat Alzheimer. Amyloid precursor protein in soluble form also has protective effects on neurons by increasing the cGMP production and activation of PKG (Urszula *et al.*, 2010). Molecular designing and synthesis of NO-donating hybrid medications, central nervous system (CNS)-targeting sGC stimulators/activators, and specific PDE inhibitors represents a significant objective in pharmacotherapy aimed at modulating NO biochemical pathways associated with cognitive functions and neuroprotective mechanisms (Zhihui., 2013).

The overexpression of eNOS results in improved function of left ventricular (LV), resulting in reduction of infarct size (Cortese-Krott *et al.*, 2022). In-vitro and in-vivo study analysis also showed that activation of cardiac proline-rich tyrosine kinase leads to inhibition of eNOS in Ischaemia-Reperfusion surgery resulting in phosphorylation of tyrosine residue of eNOS, a potential target in I/R damage reduction (Bibli *et al.*, 2017). It is also seen that reducing the synthesis of ONOO⁻ during early reperfusion can prevent the NO production. The dysregulation of NOS and its uncoupling may increase cardiac tissue damage in ischemia/reperfusion (I/R) injury by generating superoxide anion (O₂⁻) instead of NO, leading to the subsequent formation of per-oxynitrate (Matssushima & Sadoshima., 2022). Various therapeutic strategies have been employed for treatment of coronary artery diseases. One of them is the use of phosphodiesterase inhibitors that prevent the conversion of cGMP into GMP. The most widely used PDE5 inhibitor is sildenafil. PDE5i prevents the accumulation of misfolded protein by enhancing the proteasome function (Ranek *et al.*, 2013). Activators such as cinaciguat and ataciguat are used to increase the production of cGMP. Various NO donors such as sodium nitroprusside, organic nitrates are given intravenously to patients in order to decrease blood pressure and treat pulmonary hypertension. Formation of free radicals by mitochondria also leads to decreased ATP production and cell death. 6-Chromanol-derived SUL compounds can be used to maintain mitochondrial membrane potential and prevent cell death (Ataabadi *et al.*, 2020). Reactive oxygen species oxidize the cofactor BH₄ to BH₂ to decrease the production of nitric oxide by NOS. Folate supplementation increase the BH₄

bioavailability to regulate NO/cGMP cycle. Hydrogen sulfide is clinically proven to promote vasorelaxation and angiogenesis, thus reducing cardiac hypertrophy (Farah *et al.*, 2018).

During pulmonary vascular disease, there is high concentration of intracellular calcium to increase the MLCK activity. All these alterations lead to vasoconstriction of pulmonary arteries, thus inducing hypertension. Due to decreased cGMP production, cellular proliferation and platelet aggregation also disturbs the blood flow in vessels (Klinger *et al.*, 2017). Five distinct classes of drug have now been developed for the treatment of PAH i.e., prostacyclin analogues, non-prostanoid prostacyclin receptor agonists, endothelin receptor antagonists (ERAs), PDE5 inhibitors and sGC stimulators. During pulmonary arterial hypertension, superoxide is produced by various enzymes including nitroxygenase (NOX), lipoxygenase (LOX), xanthine oxidase (XO) which are also considered as the potential drug targets (Ataabadi *et al.*, 2020).

CONCLUSION

The NO/cGMP signaling pathway has tremendous effects on vasoconstriction, endothelial cell function, platelet aggregation. Biosynthesis of nitric oxide should be properly regulated to maintain cGMP production and prevent cardiovascular diseases such as pulmonary hypertension, heart failure, cardiac hypertrophy etc. All these diseases are due to either increased arginase activity or excessive production of eNOS inhibitors. In view of NO/cGMP pathway and its implicated alteration, new therapeutic strategies should be developed to enhance cognitive function in neuronal cells by preventing neurofibrillary tangle formation and maintaining cGMP metabolism in brain cells. Gene therapy techniques have also been used to target eNOS and sGC to treat such pathological disorders. Desirable pharmacological agents should be used to prevent adverse effects on normal endothelial circulation. Thus novel NO donors should be identified to be used as either neuronal or cardiovascular drugs to treat diseases of vascular system employing NO/cGMP pathway.

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